

Satellite Control System Tuned by Particle Swarm Optimization

Mawj Al-Yasiri
Cairo University, Giza, Egypt
mawjameed@yahoo.com

Mohamed Saad
Cairo University, Giza, Egypt
mssaad@gmail.com

Mohamed Moustafa Hassan
Cairo University, Giza, Egypt
Heliopolis University, Egypt
mmustafa@eng.cu.edu.eg

Abstract—This paper aims to control of satellite position using the two-phase Hybrid Stepping Motor. it's used to receive satellite signal and must accurately track the satellite as it moves across the sky. This system applies the traditional Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) control, the fuzzy PID control methods Fuzzy Logic Control (FLC) and Fractional Order PID (FOPID)control. Firstly, the PID controller and FLC was designed by Ziegler-Nichols tuning method to obtain control parameters. secondly, the PID controller and FOPID controller was designed by Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) tuning method to obtain control parameters. finally, the PID controller and FOPID controller was designed by Crazy PSO tuning method to obtain control parameters. The system was simulated by MATLAB, SIMULINK and compared be control methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the satellite communication [1], received systems are mounted on the movable device such as ship, train, car or airplane. In order to receive continuous signals, antenna system must be steered in both the azimuth and elevation angle to track a satellite. Tracking capabilities depend on the beam width of the antennas and the speed of mobile motions. In the fact that, antennas should track the satellite only in the azimuth directions because the elevation angles to the satellite are almost constant. Here getting better response of antenna position for satellite using malt controller without overshoot or steady state error and less rise time, setting time and peak time.

The paper is covering the following: Section II presents

system analysis and transfer function. Section III displays the control techniques used. Section IV review the optimization techniques. Section V illustrates simulation results. Section VI, conclude the whole work. Finally, updated list of reference is given.

II. SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND TRANSFER FUNCTION

In this paper, control of antenna tracking position used to receive satellite signal and must accurately track the satellite as it moves across the sky. antenna system must be steered in both the azimuth angle to track a satellite [2], [3], [4], pressing azimuth up and down keys, to drive a motor system. Tracking capabilities depend on the beam width of the antennas and the speed of motor move, in control terminology getting better response of antenna controller without overshoot or steady state error and less rise time, setting time and peak time.

There are two types of satellite searching methods: Mechanical and electrical. In the mechanical method [5], both elevation and azimuth angles of transmitter are controlled drive a motor system. For electronic method, searching system is done automatically by rotating the antenna according was calculated by software program.

From Fig. 1, the transfer function $G(s)$ of the open-loop system of the two-phase Hybrid Stepping Motor is as follows [6], [7].

Fig. 1. The Model of the Two-Phase Hybrid Stepping Motor

Finding the transfer function of overall system after PID control:

In order to calculate the control parameters K_p, K_i, K_D These

parameters affect the setting time, overshoot, steady-state error of the system. We have to determine transfer function of the control object. Parameters of the DC motor are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF THE DC MOTOR USED WITH SATELLITE

Parameter	Description	Value
R	Armature Resistant	2.96 Ω
L	Armature Inductance	150 mH
J	Moment of Inertia	42.3e-6 Kg.m ²
B	Viscous- Friction Coefficient	48.6e-6 Nms
Ke	Torque Constant	13.5e-3 N.m/A
K _b	Back EMV Constant	13.5e-3 V-sec/rad
N	Number of Teeth	180
β	Beta Gain	1
K _H		15
K _{PV}	Voltage Gain	500
K _{IV}	Voltage Integrator Parameter	0
K _{DV}	Voltage Defereential Parameter	100
K _{fi}	Current Integrator Parameter	500
K _{pi}	Current Gain	5

The open-loop transfer function $G(S)$ of two-phase Hybrid Stepping Motor is as follows:

$$G(S) = \frac{A(S)}{B1(S) + B2(S)} \tag{1}$$

Where

$$A(S) = \left(K_{PV} + \frac{K_{IV}}{S} + K_{DV} S \right) (K_{Pi} S + K_{Ii}) K_e N K_H$$

$$B1(S) = JLS^4 + (JR + \beta L + JK_{Pi} K_H)S^3$$

$$B2(S) = \beta K_{Pi} K_H S + (J K_{Pi} K_H + \beta R + \beta K_{Pi} K_H) S^2$$

Transfer function of the control object are calculated by the following formula:

$$G(S) = \frac{13500}{6.345S^2 + 132.498S + 326.106} \tag{2}$$

III. CONTROL TECHNIQUES

This system Proportional, Integral, and Derivative (PID), Fuzzy and Fractional Order PID (FOPID) controllers applies on multiple controller methods.

A. Proportional, Integral, and Derivative (PID) Controllers

PID were widely used in industrial control because simple structure, simple design, and low-cost, implementation have made the classical PID controller still the most popular industrial controller [8], [9]. it is the sum of three components: proportional, integral and derivative. PID parameter are K_P , K_I , K_D . Transfer function of the PID controller as illustrated in [10]:

$$G_{PID}(s) = \frac{U(s)}{E(s)} = K_P + K_I \left(\frac{1}{s} \right) + K_D s \tag{3}$$

They are many methods to tuning parameter of PID controller like hand tune, Ziegler-Nichols tuning, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) tune, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) tune and fuzzy logic, the most popular method is the Ziegler – Nichols (Z-N). In this work PID tuned by Z-N, PSO, and Crazy PSO.

B. Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC)

FLC is used in many applications such as camera, microwave, and medical industrial. fuzzy control always employs a set of rules than complex mathematical expressions those rules designed by Mamdani throughout the plant mathematical model. the used method is IF_ Then type. Inputs of fuzzy logic are error (e) and derivative of error (Δe) the outputs are controller parameters K_P , K_I , K_D the structure of fuzzy PID is two inputs and three outputs. To getting better response of antenna position interface in malt controller by anther controller.

Fuzzy PID Controller FLC will perform optimizing control parameters of PID To design FLC using ‘Mamdani’ model with two inputs(error and derivative of error) and three outputs (K_P , K_I , K_D) The member ship of function input and output used triangular shapes, the rule base of parameters using the MAX MIN (AND OR) inference in operations [11-14].

Fig. 2. Simulink diagram for Fuzzy PID controller

Fig. 3. Generic closed loop control system with the FOPID

C. Fractional Order PID (FOPID)

The intelligent optimization method. FOPID is expansion of convention PID controller based on fractional calculus [15]. The FOPID controller at first time was proposed by Podlubny in 1999 [16]. In FOPID controller beside the proportional, integral and derivative parameters K_p , K_I , K_D it has two additional parameters the order of fractional integration λ and the order of fractional derivative μ . FOPID Equation [17], [18] is shown as follows:

$$G_{FOPID}(s) = K_p + K_I s^{-\lambda} + K_D s^\mu \quad (4)$$

The λ and μ are rang terms between (0-2) with excluding [0, 1, 2].

Fig. 4. Generalization of FOPID controller

IV. OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES

To getting better response of antenna position interface in malt controller by another controller.

A. Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)

PSO is an optimization method based on stochastic technique that is developed by Dr. Eberhart and Dr. Kennedy in 1995 [19-22]. In PSO the particle is same as bird in swarm; it has position, velocity, and distance from optimal solution. The condition of each particle is changing according to three principles:

- To keep inertia of particles.
- To change the condition according to most, optimize position of particle [$Pbest$].
- To change the condition according to most, optimize position of swarm [$gbest$].

The first two steps are fairly trivial. Fitness evaluation is conducted by supplying the candidate solution to the objective function. Individual and global best fitness and positions are updated by comparing the newly evaluated fitness against the previous individual and global best fitness and replacing the

best fitness and positions as necessary. The fitness function is evaluated as shown in equation (5).

$$f(S) = \sum (\omega_1 \times E) + (\omega_2 \times \%OS) + (\omega_3 \times T_S) \quad (5)$$

Where

- E : Steady state error
- OS : Overshoot percentage
- T_S : Settling time
- $\omega_1 = 0.3$, $\omega_2 = 0.5$, and $\omega_3 = 0.2$
- $0.1 < \omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3 \leq 0.5$

The control equation [13]:

$$V_{id}^{k+1} = M.V_{id}^k + C1.rand_1[Pbest_{id} - x_{id}^k] + C2.rand_2[gbest_{id} - X_{id}^k] \quad (6)$$

$$X_{id}^{k+1} = X_{id}^k + V_{id}^{k+1} \quad (7)$$

Where $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$ where N is a number of particles in swarm, $d = 1, 2, 3, \dots, D$; where D is a number of dimensions of the particle (number of variables that optimize the fitness function), V and X are the velocity and position of particle respectively, $rand$ is random number in range (0-1), $C1$ and $C2$ are regulating constants random number rang (0 - 2), M is inertia weight constant.

This paper deals with optimization and design of an PID and FOPID controller tuned PSO.

Usually tuned of PID by Ziegler-Nichols but in this work [23], we tuned parameter of PID by PSO, PSO firstly produces initial swarm of particles in search space represented by matrix. Each particle represents a candidate solution for PID parameters where their values are set in the range of 0 to 100. For this 3-dimensional problem, position and velocity are represented by matrices with dimension of $3 \times \text{Swarm size}$ as $X = [K_p, K_I, K_D]$.

Since each FOPID controller has 5 parameters optimized with PSO. PSO algorithm searches all of the controller parameters in 5 dimensional spaces. The particle includes 5 elements assigning real values. The order of a particle is shown as follows $X = [K_p, K_I, K_D, \mu, \lambda]$.

B. Crazy Particle Swarm Optimization (CPSO)

CPSO the idea was randomizing the velocities of some of the particle referred to as crazy particles select by applying a certain probability. the probability of craziness ρ_{cr} is defined as a function of inertia weight [24]:

$$\rho_{cr} = \omega_{min} - \exp\left(-\frac{\omega^t}{\omega_{max}}\right) \quad (8)$$

A large inertia weight factor is used during initial exploration and its value is gradually reduced as the search proceeds the concept of time-varying inertial weight is given by:

$$\omega = (\omega_{max} - \omega_{min}) \times \frac{(iter_{max} - iter)}{iter_{max}} + \omega_{min} \quad (9)$$

Where

$$\omega_{max} = 0.9, \omega_{min} = 0.4$$

where $iter_{max}$ is the maximum number of iterations, to improve the convergence of PSO algorithm [25], a constriction factor is introduced. Then velocities of particles are randomized as per the following logic:

$$V_i(t) = \begin{cases} rand(0; Vmax) & \text{if } pcr \geq rand(0; 1) \\ V_i(t) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Crazy PSO such as PSO technique to tuned PID and FOPID parameters but extension randomized velocities of particles.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

Fig. 5. The step response of the PID controller and the fuzzy PID controller

Fig. 6. The step response of the PID controller tuned by PSO

Fig. 7. The step response of the FOPID controller tuned by PSO

Fig. 8. The step response of the PID controller tuned by Crazy PSO

Fig. 9. The step response of the FOPID controller tuned by Crazy PSO

The simulated results of PID controller and fuzzy controller are shown in Fig. 5. From Fig. 5, the result shows that the response of PID controller is oscillatory and long setting time, which can damage the system. But the response of fuzzy PID controller is better than PID controller.

The simulation results for all controllers are listed in Table II.

TABLE II. THE RESULT OF ALL CONTROLLERS

Controller	Peak Time (Sec)	Settling Time (Sec)	Overshoot (%)
PID	0.52	2.0	9
PID FLC	0.39	1.82	7
PID Tuned by PSO	0.17	2.4	18
FOPID Tuned by PSO	0.14	0.51	15
PID Tuned by Crazy PSO	0.13	2.5	17
FOPID Tuned by Crazy PSO	0.15	0.36	50

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the study, optimization, and performance evaluation of the satellite position. From response we can find that fuzzy PID method has better response in Overshoot characteristics of satellite position and Fractional order controllers are more flexible because they provide more parameters and perform in a better way than the integer order controllers. In this work an armature-controlled dc motor is considered. The transfer function of DC motor is being calculated for controlling its speed. There are PID types of tuning such as, PSO and Crazy PSO and more other type to improve the position of satellite response in this work we fund

PID controller tuned by PSO that batter than Ziegler-Nichols tuning.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.C.Choi, "A Study of Satellite Tracking System of DBS receiving Antenna on Ship board," Korea Maritime University Ph.D. Dissertation, 1998.
- [2] Jium-Ming-Lin, Po-Kuang Chang, "Intelligent Mobile Satellite Antenna Tracking System Design," in *SICE Annual Conference*, vol. 18, no. 5, 2008, pp. 2922-2927.
- [3] T.V. Hoi, N. T.Xuan and B. G. Duong, "Satellite tracking control system using Fuzzy PID controller," in *VNU Journal of Science: Mathematics and Physics*, vol. 31, no. 1, 2015, pp. 36-46.
- [4] Uthman, Aveen, and Shahdan Sudin, "Antenna Azimuth Position Control System using PID Controller & State-Feedback Controller Approach," in *International Journal of Electrical & Computer Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 3, 2018, pp. 2088-8708.
- [5] Jinsoo Kim, MyeongKyun Kim, Oh Yang, "Parabolic Satellite Tracking System," in the *3rd International Conference on Circuits, Control, Communication, Electricity, Electronics, Energy, System, Signal and Simulation*, vol. 25, no. 1, 2013, pp. 123-126.
- [6] UWenqiang, YAN Jianhong, "Derivation of Transmission Function Model of Two-phase Hybrid Stepping Motor," in *Space Electronic Technology*, vol. 3, no. 1, 2011, pp. 50-53.
- [7] L.A. Aloo, P.K. Kihatob and S.I. Kamauc, "DC Servomotor-based Antenna Positioning Control System Design using Hybrid PID-LQR Controller," in *European International Journal of Science and Technology*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2016, pp. 17-31.
- [8] Åström, Tore Hägglund, and Karl J. Astrom, "Advanced PID control," in *Research Triangle Park, NC: ISA-The Instrumentation, Systems, and Automation Society*, vol. 461, no.1, 2006, pp. 76-78.
- [9] Can, M.S., Ozguven, "O.F.: PID tuning with neutrosophic similarity measure," in *International Journal of Fuzzy System*, vol. 19, 2017, pp. 489-503.
- [10] Chang, Hsueh-Chia, and Liang-Heng Chen, "Bifurcation characteristics of nonlinear systems under conventional PID control," in *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 39, no. 7-8, 1984, pp. 1127-1142.
- [11] H. İ. Okumus, E. Sahin and O. Akyazi, "Antenna azimuth position control with fuzzy logic and self-tuning fuzzy logic controllers," in *8th International Conference on Electrical and Electronics Engineering (ELECO)*, 2013, pp. 477-481.
- [12] Jium-Ming Lin, Po-Kuang Chang, "Intelligent PD-Type Fuzzy Controller Design for Mobile Satellite Antenna Tracking System with Parameter Variations Effect," in *IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence in Control and Automation (CICA)*, 2011.
- [13] Sari, Naeimeh Najafizadeh, Hadi Jahanshahi, and Mahdi Fakoor, "Adaptive Fuzzy PID Control Strategy for Spacecraft Attitude Control," in *International Journal of Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 21, no. 3, 2019, pp. 769-781.
- [14] Yang, Yueneng, "Positioning control for stratospheric satellites subject to dynamics uncertainty and input constraints," in *Aerospace Science and Technology*, vol. 86, 2019, pp. 534-541.
- [15] Ahmad M. Betti, M. A. Ebrahim, M. A. Mustafa Hassan, "Modeling and Control of Stand-alone PV System Based on Fractional-Order PID Controller," in *Twentieth International Middle East Power Systems Conference (MEPCON)*, IEEE, Egypt, 2018.
- [16] B. Bonilla and J. J. Trujillo, "Fractional Order Continuity and Some Properties about Integrability ability and Differentiability of Real Functions," in *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications*, vol. 231, no. 1, 1999, pp. 205-212.
- [17] K. Tehrani, T. Capitaine, L. Barrandon, M. Hamzaoui, S. M. R. Rafiei and A. Lebrun, "Current control design with a fractional-order PID for a three-level inverter," in *14th European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications*, 2011, pp. 1-7.
- [18] R. Gorenflo and F. Mainardi, "Fractional Calculus: Integral and Differential Equations of Fractional Order," in *European International Journal of Science and Technology*, vol. 387, no. 1, 2000, pp. 223-276.
- [19] Bahgaat N.K., Moustafa Hassan M.A., "Swarm Intelligence PID Controller Tuning for AVR System," in *Advances in Chaos Theory and Intelligent Control. Studies in Fuzziness and Soft Computing*, vol. 337, 2016, pp. 791-804.
- [20] Wenxing Xu, Z. Geng, Q. Zhu and Xiangbai Gu, "A piecewise linear chaotic map and sequential quadratic programming based robust hybrid particle swarm optimization," in *Elsevier Science Inc*, vol. 218, no. 1, 2013, pp. 85-120.
- [21] Saeed Vaneshani and Hooshang Jazayeri-Rad, "Optimized Fuzzy Control by Particle Swarm Optimization Technique for Control of CSTR," in *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 59, no. 1, 2011.
- [22] Engelbrecht, Andries, "Particle swarm optimization: pitfalls and convergence aspects," in Department of Computer Science, University of Pretoria, South Africa, 2004.
- [23] Van Hoi, Tran, Nguyen Xuan Truong, and Bach Gia Duong, "Satellite tracking control system using Fuzzy PID controller," in *VNU Journal of Science: Mathematics-Physics*, vol. 31, no. 1, 2015.
- [24] Chaturvedi, Krishna Teerth, Manjaree Pandit, and Laxmi Srivastava, "Particle swarm optimization with crazy particles for nonconvex economic dispatch," in *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 9, no. 3, 2009, pp. 962-969.
- [25] Firouzi, Bahman Bahmani, et al, "A novel multi-objective Chaotic Crazy PSO algorithm for optimal operation management of distribution network with regard to fuel cell power plants," in *International Journal of Innovation Computing*, vol. 1, no. 7, 2011, pp. 6395-6409.